

CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING AND PRIVACY-PRESERVING TECHNOLOGIES FOR 6G

D3.4 EMBEDDED CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING

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Reviewer(s):	Paula Delgado de Santos (TID), Fabian Schmid (TUG), Drasko Draskovic (ABS)
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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
AMD	<i>Advanced Micro Devices</i>
API	<i>Application Programming Interface</i>
ARM	<i>Advanced RISC Machines</i>
CCA	<i>Confidential Compute Architecture (ARM)</i>
CEI	<i>Cloud, Edge and IoT</i>
CNCF	<i>Cloud Native Computing Forum</i>
CoVE	<i>Confidential Virtual Machine for RISC-V</i>
DARE	<i>Digital Autonomy with RISC-V in Europe</i>
DICE	<i>Device Identifier Composition Engine</i>
DORA	<i>Digital Operational Resilience Act</i>
DRM	<i>Digital Rights Management</i>
EHDS	<i>European Health Data Space</i>
ELF	<i>Executable and Linkable Format</i>
EPI	<i>European Processor Initiative</i>
FHE	<i>Fully Homomorphic Encryption</i>
FTT	<i>Fast Fourier Transform</i>
HHE	<i>Hybrid Homomorphic Encryption</i>
HIPAA	<i>Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act</i>
HPC	<i>High-Performance Computing</i>
HW	<i>Hardware</i>
IEC	<i>International Electrotechnical Commission</i>
IoT	<i>Internet of Things</i>
IPR	<i>Intellectual Property Right</i>
ISA	<i>Instruction Set Architecture</i>
ISO	<i>International Organization for Standardization</i>
ITS	<i>Intelligent Transportation System</i>
MCU	<i>Microcontroller Unit</i>

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MFP	<i>Mixed-Filter-Permutator</i>
ML	<i>Machine Learning</i>
MLaaS	<i>Machine Learning as a Service</i>
NPU	<i>Neural Processing Unit</i>
NTT	<i>Number Theoretic Transform</i>
OP-TEE	<i>Open-source TEE by Linaro</i>
PC	<i>Personal Computer</i>
PCR	<i>Platform Configuration Register (in TPM)</i>
PHI	<i>Protected Health Information</i>
PMP	<i>Physical Memory Protection (RISC-V)</i>
PoBF	<i>Proof of Being Forgotten</i>
PoCF	<i>PoBF-Compliant Framework</i>
PPFL	<i>Privacy-Preserving Federated Learning</i>
RISC	<i>Reduced Instruction Set Computer</i>
RISC-V	<i>RISC 5 (the fifth generation)</i>
RLWE	<i>Ring Learning With Errors</i>
RSA	<i>Rivest Shamir Adleman</i>
RSU	<i>Road-Side Unit</i>
SDK	<i>Software Development Kit</i>
SEV	<i>Secure Encrypted Virtualization (AMD)</i>
SGX	<i>Software Guard Extensions (Intel)</i>
SIM	<i>Subscriber Identity Module</i>
SIMD	<i>Single-Instruction-Multiple-Data</i>
SM	<i>Security Monitor</i>
SoC	<i>System on Chip</i>
STRIDE	<i>Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information disclosure, Denial of service, Elevation of privilege</i>
TA	<i>Trusted Application (ARM TrustZone)</i>
TCG	<i>Trusted Computing Group</i>
TDX	<i>Trust Domain Extensions (Intel)</i>

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TEE	<i>Trusted Execution Environment</i>
TLS	<i>Transport Layer Security</i>
TPM	<i>Trusted Platform Module</i>
V2X	<i>Vehicle-to-Everything</i>
WAMR	<i>WebAssembly Micro Runtime</i>
WASI	<i>WebAssembly System Interface</i>
WASM	<i>WebAssembly</i>
WiSARD	<i>Wilkie, Stonham, and Aleksander's Recognition Device</i>

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Confidential computing is a paradigm designed to protect data not only at rest and in transit but also during active processing. While traditionally associated with cloud environments, where it enables secure deployment of computing workloads for improved performance, scalability, and cost-efficiency, its applications are expanding into other domains.

This document explores the applicability of confidential computing technologies in resource-constrained embedded systems, evaluating both software-based approaches (Fully Homomorphic Encryption) and hardware-based solutions (Trusted Execution Environments). A short overview of confidential computing enablers, especially for ARM and RISC-V platforms, is given.

Key use cases are presented, particularly in secure edge computing, where latency constraints, limited bandwidth, or large data volumes require local processing at the edge or along the edge-cloud continuum. In embedded systems, code confidentiality can be as critical as data confidentiality, especially when proprietary algorithms are deployed in physically insecure or even hostile environments. The study also highlights confidential computing use cases across verticals such as automotive, healthcare, military, and financial services, emphasizing the unique security requirements of each.

While cloud-based confidential computing often relies on confidential virtual machines for ease of deployment, embedded systems typically adopt a lighter-weight protected application/process model that demands more customization but fits within tighter resource constraints.

The document also details experimental work with Keystone enclaves on the RISC-V platform, including methods for deploying encrypted native code workloads or running lightweight runtimes for Python or WebAssembly with optional encryption support. Although Fully Homomorphic Encryption remains computationally intensive for embedded devices, the report explores hybrid models where client-side operations are performed locally and offloaded to cloud services for secure computation. Benchmark results for client-side operations and the Homomorphic WiSARDs framework are also included.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 SCOPE

This is an analysis document on the feasibility of the use of Confidential Computing in resource-constrained platforms. The document is a deliverable of the CONFIDENTIAL6G project task 3.4 Embedded Confidential Computing. The task has investigated confidential computing methodologies on constrained end nodes. The task has examined how to provide a scaled-down confidential computing enclave, supporting remote attestation for microcontroller-class IoT devices that include security hardware (e.g., ARM TrustZone for ARMv8-M or RISC-V security features) like Trusted Execution Environment (TEE). Additionally, the task has investigated the feasibility of using Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) on resource-constrained platforms. Use cases for embedded confidential computing are also described. Finally, we discuss tooling, tests, and verification procedures, proving that the delivered functionalities are included.

1.2 DOCUMENT ORGANIZATION

The document is organized as follows. Section 2 gives an overview of Embedded Confidential Computing topics and CONFIDENTIAL6G approaches. In Section 3 use cases of Embedded Confidential Computing are described. Section 4 is discussing utilization of various TEEs to implement Embedded Confidential Computing platforms. Practical experiments with TEE-based approaches are described in Section 5. Feasibility of FHE is discussed in Section 6. Concluding remarks are given in Section 7.

2 BACKGROUND

Confidential Computing is a mechanism that aims to protect data in use in addition to more common protection of data in transit (encrypted communications and integrity protection) and protection of data at rest (encrypted storage and integrity protection). The concept has become especially popular in cloud environments as organizations want to outsource their computation tasks to powerful cloud services but require guarantees that the confidentiality of sensitive data is still maintained.

2.1 THREAT MODEL

A threat model includes a definition of a protection target and classifies various attack categories to be either in scope or out of scope. CONFIDENTIAL6G report D3.1 [1] includes a STRIDE¹-based threat model analysis with mitigation strategies and examples both for TEE and FHE based confidential computing approaches. The analysis is still valid also for embedded confidential computing but embedded confidential computing is focusing less on centralized cloud computing services and more on decentralized IoT devices. This also means that a lack of physical security must be taken into account even more than in centralized cloud service use cases.

2.1.1 PROTECTION TARGETS

The primary objective is to ensure that sensitive data and code remain confidential and unaltered, even in the presence of threats.

- **Data confidentiality** – Confidentiality of data must be preserved. This is a primary protection target as confidential data is transferred and processed in a remote system. The use of encryption and encrypted communications and processing data either in TEE or by utilizing FHE should be used to protect data confidentiality.
- **Data integrity** – All unauthorized modifications must be detected and preferably prevented. Stored data and communication messages should

¹ Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information disclosure, Denial of service, Elevation of privilege

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include cryptographic signing and verification tasks that can detect modifications.

- **Code confidentiality** – Also executable code should optionally be confidentiality protected. This is generally not always needed as confidential items are cryptographic keys and confidential application data that are only available during process run time. However, in some cases software code implementing confidential algorithm should be protected.
- **Code integrity** – All unauthorized modifications to code must be detected and preferably prevented. Software components should be verified before passing control using either secure boot or trusted boot mechanisms and remote attestation should be used when communicating with remote parties.

Additional targets

- **Device identity** – Device nodes should have secure identity that cannot be forged and copied to a malicious “digital twin”.
- **Trusted Computing Base (TCB) minimization** – In order to keep attack surface small, the size of the trusted computing base should be kept minimal.

2.1.2 ATTACK CATEGORIES

Confidential Computing Consortium threat model [2] specifies the following attack categories to be in scope.

- **Software attacks** – Attacks utilizing found vulnerabilities in software components.
- **Protocol attacks** – Attacks related to modification, replay, and denial of communication messages.
- **Cryptographic attacks** – Attacks utilizing mathematical breakthroughs, advances in computing power, and new approaches (e.g., quantum computing) to be able to break cryptographic protection.
- **Basic physical attacks** – Bus and cache monitoring, plugging attack devices to existing device ports.
- **Basic upstream supply-chain attacks** – For example, a large batch of misconfigured product devices having debug ports active.

The following attacks are listed to be out of scope.

- **Sophisticated physical attacks** – Attacks requiring well-equipped laboratory tools like chip scraping techniques and electron microscope probes.
- **Upstream hardware supply-chain attacks** – Attacks at chip manufacturing time.

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- **Availability attacks** – As availability, e.g., connection to a remote node, also depends on non-secure side of the system, it is not possible to protect using secure-side software. Availability issues are left out from the threat model.

Side-channel attacks are not explicitly mentioned, but the threat model discussion contains a separate section for various side-channel attacks. The document also mentions that preventing side-channel attacks is collectively the responsibility of the TEE vendors, third-party vendors, and application developers.

2.2 CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING CONCEPTS

Confidential computing is based on concepts that we briefly introduce in this section. These concepts are building blocks for systems implementing confidential computing.

Encryption is a cryptographic building block that allows the transformation of a plaintext m into a ciphertext c such that c remains secure against unauthorized parties. In contrast, the rightful key k allows for recovery of the plaintext m via a decryption procedure. An encryption scheme is defined by three algorithms: KGen, Enc, and Dec. The key generation algorithm KGen gets as input a security parameter λ and outputs a secret key k . The encryption algorithm Enc is a probabilistic algorithm that takes k and a message m as input and outputs a ciphertext c . The decryption algorithm Dec is a deterministic algorithm that takes as input a key k and a ciphertext c and outputs a message m . An Encryption scheme commonly fulfils correctness, such that condition $\Pr[Dec(k, Enc(k, m)) = m] = 1$ holds (with computational relaxation). The common security notion for Encryption schemes is indistinguishability under a chosen plaintext attack. This model assumes a probabilistic polynomial time adversary with an encryption oracle $Enc(k, *)$, which must distinguish between the ciphertexts of two messages of its choice. We assume, that the scheme is secure, if the adversary can only do so with negligible probability.

Isolation is a security mechanism that separates computing processes and execution environments to ensure that a compromise in one component does not compromise the integrity or confidentiality of others. It protects against adversaries by confining potential breaches within isolated compartments, preventing lateral movement, and limiting access to sensitive resources. Software-based isolation techniques - such as containerization, microkernel architectures, and hypervisor-driven virtualization - implement strict access controls and resource partitioning to confine processes to dedicated environments, reducing the attack surface and mitigating risk even if one component is compromised. In parallel, hardware

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isolation leverages advanced processor features such as Intel SGX [3] and AMD SEV-SNP [4] to create secure isolated enclaves.

Remote attestation is a security mechanism that allows a device to prove its identity and integrity to a remote device or server. It works by having the device generate a cryptographic report containing details of its configuration, software status, and security measures, often using digital certificates and secure protocols. This report is then sent in response to a verification request from the remote party, which compares the report to trusted benchmarks or policies. If the report meets the expected criteria, the remote device can trust that the certifying device has not been tampered with, ensuring secure communication and interaction. This process is critical to prevent unauthorized access, data breaches and malicious activity in networked environments.

Confidential virtual machines and enclaves are trusted environments that protect data by isolating workloads from potentially untrusted infrastructure. They leverage hardware-based security features - such as those found in Intel SGX, AMD SEV, or emerging standards such as Intel TDX [5] - to create TEEs where both code and data remain shielded from unauthorized access, even if the underlying host is compromised. Using encryption for system memory and CPU registers in addition to enforcing strict isolation boundaries, these technologies ensure that computations can run confidentially in multi-tenant and cloud-native environments. This is now a widely used concept and there are recipes how this can be used with main cloud system providers [6].

2.3 CONFIDENTIAL6G DUAL APPROACH

Confidential6G is investigating both software- and hardware-based approaches to provide confidential processing environment.

A TEE is a secure area within a device's processor that protects sensitive data and computational operations from unauthorized access. It is built using specific techniques such as hardware isolation, secure boot, and cryptographic verification. Hardware isolation creates a separate space for critical tasks, keeping them hidden from the main operating system. Secure boot ensures that only trusted software is loaded during startup, while cryptographic verification (e.g., using encryption and decryption) maintains data integrity. OP-TEE [7] for ARM TrustZone or the Intel SGX SDK [8] for Intel platforms are suitable for practical TEE development. OP-TEE is widely used in various embedded systems and mobile devices requiring TEEs to support tasks like secure firmware updates, digital rights management, and secure

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boot. Intel SGX is deployed by cloud providers like Microsoft Azure to provide confidential cloud computing services.

FHE enables the computation of arbitrary functions over encrypted data without decrypting the data. That is, given encryptions $E(m_1), \dots, E(m_t)$, one can compute $f(m_1, \dots, m_t)$ for messages (m_1, \dots, m_t) , without compromising the confidentiality and privacy of the messages. In TEEs or resource-constrained devices, this property is critical for maintaining confidentiality while allowing outsourcing of computations to untrusted nodes. FHE schemes typically rely on lattice-based cryptographic primitives, which support homomorphic addition and multiplication on ciphertexts. Industrial frameworks (e.g., IBM Helib [9], Microsoft SEAL [10]) integrate these features, offering practical implementations for secure data processing in TEEs or other constrained platforms.

2.4 RESOURCE-CONSTRAINED PLATFORMS

Confidential computing is typically used to outsource computing tasks to centralized powerful cloud services while still maintaining control for data confidentiality. Threat landscape in these cases is typically related to trust for cloud service providers. Confidential computing is used to mitigate threats related to malicious cloud service provider, cloud service personnel, system software, and hardware platforms. Computing hardware in cloud environment includes large amount of memory, practically infinite amount of storage, and fast multicore computers.

Embedded systems that are used, e.g., in edge computing, have very different characteristics. The systems are typically decentralized, and nodes are in a wide geographic area. This considerably increases physical attack threats. The devices used in edge computing can be either general-purpose devices or devices that are built for specific purposes. Typically, also there is less memory and storage size is limited. These limitations may rule out the deployment of large ML models inside embedded devices and deploying the models to a TEE inside an embedded device has even more limitations. Computers may also have fewer cores and processing speed is slower. Data communications are also relying on narrowband connections with limited data transfer capacity. Especially mobile nodes may also have power consumption constraints. Because of these platform constraints, application software development may require considerable porting effort to make the algorithm run efficiently in resource-poor environments.

Edge computing [11] is typically applied to situations where there are strict latency requirements that make it impossible to tolerate round-trip delays to external

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computing services. Sometimes the calculation of extremely large data sets must also be done locally, as there is only a narrowband channel to external services.

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3 USE CASES FOR EMBEDDED CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING

In this Section we are listing potential use cases for embedded confidential computing. A basic use case for confidential computing is to dynamically add capacity for computing tasks by uploading the task to a cloud service while still maintaining control for data confidentiality. The use of cloud services typically provides scalability, flexibility, and cost savings while still maintaining data confidentiality [12]. Embedded confidential computing use cases are more diverse.

3.1 SECURE EDGE COMPUTING

Confidentiality protection target: Protect confidential data that is processed at the edge node and provide confidential computing environment across edge-to-cloud continuum.

There is a growing interest to extend cloud-based confidential computing environments to cover also edge nodes that are physically closer to a user and are not physically located in data centres of the cloud providers. Sometimes edge computing platforms are also classified as near edge and far edge nodes. Near edge nodes can be nodes that are located in customer premises (e.g., in a local office) and far edge nodes can be nodes located in third-party locations (e.g., various IoT devices). However, that does not radically change the trust assumptions as in a cloud-based confidential computing the cloud service provider can also be considered as an attacker. Motivation to extend confidential computing can be latency requirements, a need to avoid large data transfers to cloud services over narrowband connections, or cost savings in communications over expensive links. Once such an extension exists, it is also possible to use underutilized edge nodes as an additional computing capacity and orchestrate computing tasks also to these nodes.

There are many research activities and projects that are tackling this issue. The European Cloud Edge IoT Continuum Initiative [13] is promoting cooperation between actors to develop a technological paradigm that could be used to investigate and develop a continuum that could span Cloud, Edge, and IoT nodes (CEI). There are two coordination and support actions: OpenContinuum [14], focusing on the supply side, and UNLOCK-CEI [15], focusing on the demand side.

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Large cloud service providers have started to offer also secure edge computing facilities. For example, Microsoft Azure IoT Edge [16] includes cross-platform Open Enclave SDK [17] that supports Intel SGX and ARM TrustZone-based TEEs. However, in addition to a qemu² emulator, there is only one certified edge device, ARM TrustZone-based Scalys TrustBox [18], that is certified for Azure IoT use. Linaro, which is ARM ecosystem company, has developed concepts for the use of confidential AI for microcontroller units (MCUs) [19] by utilizing ARM platform. Ideally, it should be possible to orchestrate an unmodified computing workload to an optimal location in a continuum based on a cost function that could depend on data transfer and latency constraints. However, in practice this is challenging as runtime platforms in a continuum have very different characteristics and constraints. Cross-platform SDKs typically support only 2-3 platforms.

Figure 1. Cloud, Edge and the Internet of Things continuum (based on [20])

² <https://qemu.org>

3.2 PROPRIETARY ALGORITHM PROTECTION

Confidentiality protection target: An algorithm, e.g., an ML model, that is widely distributed to multiple physical locations and contains high-value IPR that should be protected against competitors and other misuse.

Embedded devices may include local processing that is utilizing proprietary algorithms, providing a competitive advantage for a manufacturer, and that should be protected against leaks to competitors. Using legal means, e.g., patenting, may not always be feasible [21]. For example, a specific Machine Learning (ML) model may be the result of expensive training, and the model should be protected against copying and reverse engineering. Possible example is an industrial equipment that is doing intelligent monitoring. Because of latency requirements, data volume or narrow communication channel processing must be done locally. In these cases, input data may not be confidential as it can be environmental measurements like temperature, humidity, or air pressure. However, output values typically need protection as those can be used together with input values to reverse engineer the algorithm.

If the proprietary algorithm is run in hardware-based TEE, then the attackers are not able to directly copy the algorithm if the algorithm is implemented as model parameters, e.g., internal variables of an ML model that are learned from the training data. The parameters for the algorithm can then be deployed to TEE by utilizing a secure channel, e.g., Transport Layer Security (TLS) with remote attestation support and then optionally stored into the device encrypted with a device-specific symmetric key that is derived from the device secret. Memory isolation between TEE and the rest of the system is protecting confidential data from being exposed to an attacker that has been able to penetrate to a system and has full access to system software including kernel.

If the algorithm is implemented as a program code, the protection is more challenging as embedded platforms typically do not provide confidential virtual machine abstractions that could include fully encrypted virtual machines. Resource-constrained platforms typically do not have hardware support for memory encryption/decryption, and memory constraints may also make it impossible to include a full operating system on the TEE-side. TEE approaches for embedded devices, e.g., ARM TrustZone, focus more on code integrity, but some implementations, e.g., OP-TEE [7], also provide optional encryption for Trusted Applications (TAs) running in TEE environment. Leaving sensitive executable binaries unencrypted is exposing those to disassembler attacks and reverse engineering [22].

Figure 2. Prevent reverse engineering of sensitive algorithms by keeping the code encrypted

Another approach, especially in devices including a Trusted Platform Module (TPM), is to implement secure boot with a sealed key that can be used to decrypt the application. The application can only be decrypted using the sealed key if the secure boot state matches the expected secure state. Alternatively, the code may be dynamically downloaded to the device after the device state has been verified by remote attestation. In both cases, the decrypted application should be installed into a volatile partition so that the installed application is not available for offline analysis. Code obfuscation is sometimes used to implement copy protection (e.g., for computer games) and it can also be used to obfuscate code that implements algorithms that need to be protected from reverse engineering.

3.3 AUTOMOTIVE SYSTEMS

Confidentiality protection target: User-related data or user identity collected by connected vehicles and road-side infrastructure.

Modern cars collect lots of sensor data that can also reveal information about the user. The most obvious are location information and typical travel habits. At the same time there is a growing interest to build road-side infrastructure known as Road-Side Units (RSUs) that could also communicate with these connected cars [23]. RSUs can be used to monitor traffic/road conditions and issue information messages to road traffic. There is also an Intelligent Transportation System (ITS) vision, where connected vehicles and RSUs with Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communications could improve road safety by implementing complex manoeuvres like lane-change operations or traffic crossing management. ITS and V2X include lots of security and privacy issues [24], [25]. Attackers may utilize vulnerabilities in communications stacks of cars and road-side infrastructure and be able to affect to road traffic and also cause safety issues. Automotive infrastructure needs effective protection against cyber-attacks, strong device identities to prevent

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unauthorized actors but at the same time also protection for unwanted data collection is needed. Cybersecurity issues of smart cars, including privacy issues of data sources, are discussed in a report [26] by Enisa³.

Many times, an idea pops up that car users should pay a congestion fee when driving on certain roads at certain times. Although this can be implemented by monitoring vehicles entering and leaving a toll zone region, there are arguments that a more fine-grained method is needed, as a simple mechanism does not account for how much the vehicle is driving inside the toll zone region. Connected vehicle could have a mechanism to calculate such a fee without exposing all detailed driving information to a centralized service. The user should be able to verify that a fair fee is charged based on driving details inside the toll zone. However, also the authorities need to have evidence that toll-zone driving is correctly measured, but they should not get details.

So far, congestion fee systems have been implemented as toll fee for crossing the toll area boundary. This is because there has been a lack of reliable positioning infrastructure. However, 5G/6G-based systems with ITS/V2X should change that, and in general, the vehicle could have quite accurate position information.

The automotive industry has many sector-specific standards, but there is also an interest to use more generic, trusted computing building blocks [27].

³ <https://enisa.europa.eu>

Figure 3. Smart car ecosystem

3.4 HEALTHCARE APPLICATIONS

Confidentiality protection target: Patient data privacy and proprietary analysis algorithms.

Personal health data should be protected if it is uploaded to cloud services. Another alternative is to process it locally. There is lots of regulation like the proposed European Health Data Space (EHDS) and Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) Privacy and Security Rules in USA. Hartmann et al. [28] list reasons for the use of edge computing in healthcare systems mentioning cost, low latency, location awareness, energy efficiency, and usability. They also list few security reasons. Alzu'bi et al. [29] have also given a survey of privacy issues,

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challenges, and research directions of healthcare related edge computing. The survey does not mention any TEE-based confidential computing issues to solve the listed challenges, but FHE is mentioned as well as searchable encryption [30].

Figure 4. Example of protecting healthcare AI workloads [31]

A blog article [31] describes the use of Fortanix tools to secure healthcare AI by using confidential computing techniques. Although the articles do not explicitly deal with embedded confidential computing issues, it is mentioned that Protected Health Information (PHI) must stay protected during the whole lifecycle. This can also be applied to the device-edge-cloud continuum. Securing analysis algorithms of personal health measurements could also be one topic.

3.5 MILITARY EQUIPMENT APPLICATIONS

Confidentiality protection target: Military equipment system software, key material, and collected data.

Military equipment, like drones, are operating in hostile environments. There is also a need to support autonomous low-latency operations as delays in control and cuts in communications would endanger the device. The devices should also be able to perform local analysis utilizing advanced data fusion technologies. Therefore, it is crucially important that the devices contain encryption mechanisms so that details of system software components cannot be reverse-engineered by the enemy or even have the ability to self-destruct so that key material is also removed. One way

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to implement these requirements is to run the whole system volatile media and provision critical key material and critical algorithms to TEEs just before the mission. Ukraine war has shown rapid increase of AI-driven unmanned systems [32]. Various cybersecurity issues of drones are also discussed in [33] and [34].

Details of military equipment are typically not available in public. However, there are examples of civilian use of confidential computing technologies for edge devices that may end up being used as dual use technology also in military products. One such example is Swiss company Cysec⁴ and their drones that are using confidential computing, hardened OS, and containerized workloads [35].

There are also other confidentiality aspects as capabilities of military equipment are increasingly based on software. Equipment manufacturers and a country that is selling military equipment may want to retain control. Military equipment is sold to a customer, but the customer may not be fully trusted as the manufacturer may not have full control to personnel that has access to the equipment. Sometimes the customer may even become an enemy. In these cases, confidential computing could be used to avoid exposing most sensitive details and key material to personnel that is not fully trusted.

3.6 FINANCIAL APPLICATIONS

Confidentiality protection target: User identity, financial transaction credentials, and business rules for trading transactions.

Nowadays, there are multiple financial transaction alternatives that are providing more smooth way to make payments than classic cash or debit/credit card payments. Typically, a mobile wallet has been moved to a person's gadget like a mobile phone or a watch and implementing confidentiality-protected processing in these devices.

Another financial use case for confidential computing is so-called low-latency algorithmic trading, where marketplace (e.g., stock market) transactions are made using pre-programmed rules in computing edge nodes having fast network connection to the market exchange services. Often, this leads to a minimization of network routers in the end-to-end connection and placing the server on untrusted

⁴ <https://cysec.com>

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premises to minimize physical distance. There can also be other trust issues such as hiding the business transaction rules from computing staff. This use case resembles the traditional cloud use case, but instead of moving computing task to a centralized cloud service, computing is transferred to a low-latency edge node.

There are also financial sector regulations that can be seen even to mandate the protection of data in use in the financial sector. For example, the EU has the Digital Operational Resilience Act (DORA) [36] that in Article 9, paragraph 2 states: “Financial entities shall design, procure and implement ICT security policies, procedures, protocols and tools that aim to ensure the resilience, continuity and availability of ICT systems, in particular for those supporting critical or important functions, and to maintain high standards of availability, authenticity, integrity and confidentiality of data, whether at rest, in use or in transit”. This means that banks should move their existing cloud-based computing workloads to confidential computing cloud services, increasing demand for confidential virtual machine based cloud infrastructure.

4 TEES AND CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Confidential computing can be implemented using a hardware-based approach based on TEE that provides an isolated execution environment for confidential workloads, integrity verification, remote attestation, and platform identity.

4.2 ORIGINS OF HARDWARE-BASED CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING

Hardware-based confidential computing originates from trusted computing concepts. The development history, divided to three stages, is described in Figure 5 adapted from Feng et al. [37].

4.2.1 THE FIRST PHASE: TPM

The original target was to develop technologies that allow remote parties to verify integrity and authenticity of a remote computer before allowing the computer to access remote services. This use case is known as remote attestation mechanisms. This was first implemented using a small, trusted hardware component that included cryptographic keys, signing capability, Platform Configuration Registers (PCRs) that were used to protect integrity measurements, and few other functions. Trusted hardware is also integrated with a boot mechanism in such a way that integrity of the next boot phase firmware is verified before passing control to the next phase. This fixed function TEE approach was standardized by Trusted Computing Group (TCG) with Trusted Platform Module (TPM) specifications that are now also standardized by the International Organization for Standardization/International Electrotechnical Commission (ISO/IEC) [38]. Although TPM fixed functionality is very limited, it allowed development of primitive confidential computing functionality that could locally verify platform integrity before proceeding. For example, TPM sealing functionality allows decryption only if the required conditions are met referring to a state of the PCRs.

4.2.2 THE SECOND PHASE: TEE

The second phase in the analysis of Feng et al. [37] is a programmable trusted execution environment. Instead of standardized fixed functions, this approach is providing an isolated integrity and confidentiality protected environment to run small programs. ARM TrustZone [39] became popular, especially in mobile phones, allowing device manufacturers to deploy small Trusted Applications (TAs) for

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specific tasks like cellular network Subscriber Identity Module (SIM) lock and Digital Rights Management (DRM) license management. The concept was also standardized by an industry consortium Global Platform that provided specifications for core functionality (e.g., [40]). Although the ARM TrustZone concept allowed third-party TAs, device manufacturers were acting as gatekeepers and were not willing to risk isolation by allowing third-party TAs limiting wider use of this technology [41]. Intel developed Software Guard Extensions (SGX) [3] that provided isolated processes and a more open deployment model that was also used in cloud computing.

Figure 5. The development history of trusted and confidential computing.

4.2.3 THE THIRD PHASE: CONFIDENTIAL VIRTUAL MACHINE

Although TEEs could provide a cloud-based confidential computing platform, it was recognized that the concept also has many drawbacks. The original TEE concept (e.g., ARM TrustZone) was based on the idea that the application should be partitioned into secure world and non-secure world parts keeping the secure part

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(TA) small to limit the size of a trusted computing base and an attack surface. TAs must also use specific APIs, like TEE Internal Core API [42] specification with ARM TrustZone, adding porting work for an application. There are also many memory limitations. Applications also depend on many operating system services that need to be emulated. Device manufacturers also typically did not offer the opportunity to run own TAs in ARM TrustZone SecureWorld. Intel SGX enclaves could be used by third parties and became popular in confidential cloud computing.

AMD did not follow Intel's SGX approach but developed a confidential virtual machine concept called Secure Encrypted Virtualization (SEV) [4]. SEV allowed users to run the whole operating system with unmodified applications. This allowed easy deployment of existing applications to cloud-based confidential computing platforms. Both Intel and ARM are now also providing similar confidential virtual machine approaches. Intel Trust Domain Extensions (TDX) [5] provides SEV-like functionality and ARM Confidential Compute Architecture (CCA) [43] extends the ARM TrustZone architecture. There is also a specification called Confidential Virtual Machine for RISC-V platforms (CoVE) [44] that specifies similar architecture for RISC-V platform.

4.3 EMBEDDED CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING PLATFORMS

Embedded devices are typically designed to use very different architectures compared to typical Intel/AMD based PC platforms. There are multiple reasons to avoid PC platform CPUs. Typical reasons are:

1. **Cost** – CPU chips for PCs are typically more expensive than specialized low-end microcontrollers and System on Chips (SoCs) that can be used to implement required functionality in embedded systems.
2. **Power consumption and heat** – Many embedded systems are designed to operate on low power without access to mains power. Devices may be battery powered, use energy harvest, or require charging. Intel and AMD CPUs consume too much power to be suitable for many embedded system designs. Intel/AMD CPUs also generate more heat and require additional cooling solutions.
3. **Specificity** - Embedded systems are designed for specific tasks and often require real-time processing. Microcontrollers and SoCs are tailored for these tasks, whereas Intel and AMD CPUs are designed for general-purpose computing.
4. **Integration** – Embedded system design can use SoCs that integrate support for many peripheral interfaces.

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Embedded platforms typically have less support for virtualization, making SEV/TDX-like confidential virtual machine approach inconvenient.

4.3.1 ARM PLATFORMS

ARM is the most successful platform for embedded systems because of power efficiency. ARM chips are especially used in mobile devices like smartphones and tablets and other consumer electronic devices like smart TVs, gaming consoles, and wearable devices. Industrial automation, automotive, and IoT are also utilizing ARM chips.

ARM platforms can include isolated execution environment based on ARM TrustZone technology [39]. ARM TrustZone provides support for TAs that are running in an isolated TEE called SecureWorld. SecureWorld can be accessed from the rest of the system (also known as NormalWorld) using a client API that is specified by Global Platform. Global Platform has also developed a specification for internal API that TAs can use. Open-source implementation OP-TEE [7] is used in many embedded systems and popular Raspberry Pi development boards. There are also alternatives for Global Platform APIs. Google is using Trusty TEE [45] with Android. Trusty has its own APIs.

Figure 6. ARM TrustZone architecture

ARM has also TEE solutions for microcontroller class devices that are more lightweight and run either bare metal applications or small operating system like Zephyr [46] or FreeRTOS [47]. ARM TrustZone-M [48] can be used with a device secret and layered security approach called Device Identifier Composition Engine (DICE) [49].

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All these ARM platforms can be used to implement a processing environment for confidential data. However, provisioning new workloads for these platforms has been a weak point so far. Configurations are typically static, and the environment is typically used only by device manufacturers. This is now changing with ARM CCA [43] that provides Realms for third-party TAs.

4.3.2 RISC-V PLATFORMS

RISC-V platform is nowadays a main alternative for ARM in embedded systems [50]. The main benefit is an open Instruction Set Architecture (ISA). RISC-V based systems can be developed without having to pay for licenses and royalties to ISA owners. Open ISA has made RISC-V especially popular in academia as it can be freely used and extended to create research prototypes.

RISC-V standardization is coordinated by an organization called RISC-V International. RISC-V provides a standardized low-level isolation mechanism called Physical Memory Protection (PMP) that can be used to partition physical memory into protected zones. PMP is a part of privileged ISA specification [51] (the latest ratified version). RISC-V International has also other draft specifications for isolation. CoVE [44] specification provides support for confidential virtual machines. RISC-V international has standardized a large number of extensions. This has caused some confusion as it is not so easy to find out, which extensions are needed. Therefore, RISC-V International has published two profiles called RVA23 and RVB23. The RVA23 profile is designed for high-performance, compute-intensive applications and requires mandatory vector and hypervisor extensions, ensuring a consistent and efficient software ecosystem. RVB23 is more flexible, allowing a broader range of optional extensions.

There are open-source RISC-V chip designs like Berkeley Rocket Chip Generator [52] SoCs that can be deployed to FPGA platforms [53]. However, although RISC-V ISA is an open standard there is no requirement to publish the design as open source. Chip implementations following RISC-V ISA can be proprietary. Because of technology sanctions, RISC-V has gained lots of interest among Chinese manufacturers. There are also European research projects like European Processor Initiative (EPI) [54] and Digital Autonomy with RISC-V in Europe (DARE) [55] that are developing RISC-V based designs especially for High-Performance Computing (HPC).

PMP is typically supported in low-end RISC-V devices to provide an isolation mechanism. This feature has been used to implement RISC-V Keystone Enclaves [56]. PMP is also used in Espressif ESP-TEE [57] that is targeted for microcontroller

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class Espressif ESP32-C6 RISC-V systems with a support for a separate rich OS (e.g., FreeRTOS) and a trusted OS combination.

4.3.3 FPGA PLATFORMS

FPGA can be used to implement algorithm-specific accelerators especially if it is possible to utilize parallelism. FPGA-based design can also include general-purpose processor cores, so-called soft cores, but those are considerably slower. There are also activities to build confidential computing enclaves using FPGA platforms [58], [59]. Cloud providers are also offering FPGA platforms for their customers.

Shielded Enclaves for Cloud FPGAs (ShEF) [60] is a TEE for cloud-based reconfigurable accelerators targeted for a use case where the adversary has physical access to the system and is also able to manipulate many things. ShEF provides secure boot and remote attestation. A specific customizable component called Shield provides secure access to data for accelerator implementations.

MeetGo - A trusted execution environment for remote applications on FPGA [61] is another example of FPGA-based TEE. MeetGo includes a remote attestation mechanism that can verify the integrity of the applications. There is also an isolation mechanism to block unauthorized access to the applications from the malicious CPU and secure communication mechanism to allow secure transmissions of sensitive data between the installed applications and remote users. These features are backed by a hardware trust anchor.

4.4 TOOLS

4.4.1 PLATFORM BUILD TOOLS

Embedded systems can use build tools that can build a complete firmware image from source code packages. Buildroot [62] is used to cross-compile source code packages to target architecture using user-defined configuration specifications. Buildroot can generate a root filesystem, a Linux kernel image, and a bootloader for a target device. Yocto [63] is another popular build tool for embedded system firmware image generation utilizing its own BitBake build engine. Buildroot is simpler and faster tool whereas Yocto is more flexible and is suitable for complex large-scale projects. Yocto can also be used to generate a complete Software Development Kit (SDK) for the device platform. Both buildroot and Yocto can be seen as specific examples of platform engineering tools where software image is built based on user-specified configuration settings. This is also common practice with containers (e.g., Docker), where a base image can be selected with additional customizations. Confidential computing build typically requires specific kernel

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version/branch, a dedicated kernel configuration, additional packages, and a set of patches to different packages. There are also lots of tools targeted for platform engineering and platform orchestration [64].

4.4.2 TESTING AND VERIFICATION PROCEDURES

Confidential computing frameworks are using integrity verification and remote attestation to verify the integrity of the system components. IETF RATS WG is developing standards for remote attestation architecture and formats, but there are lots of platform dependencies that complicate the development of these systems.

The Certifier framework for confidential computing [65], [66] is tackling problems like hardware diversity and software complexity by developing a unified framework and providing support for multiple platforms. The Certifier project has developed a certifier library with basic functionality and adapters for many confidential computing platforms. There is also a certifier service that allows confidential computing programs to be deployed and managed in a simple, scalable manner.

Figure 7. Certifier framework architecture

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Project Veraison [67] is building an Attestation Service that includes reference integrity metrics for different platforms. Remote party can delegate verification to Veraison Attestation Service.

However, the use of these verification frameworks only provides confidence that the integrity of the underlying systems is correct, but this does not rule out any vulnerabilities or backdoors in a system. System building blocks may consist of proprietary system components and there is no source code available to review the behaviour. The Transparency concept [68] is meant to specify different degrees of transparency that could help to build trust in confidential computing systems. The authors propose a three-level transparency hierarchy that is described in Table 1. Open sourcing provides highest transparency, but the authors also present certification alternatives for closed-source modules.

Table 1. Transparency levels

Level	Transparency agents	Trust-building blocks
1	First-party certifiers	Endorsement statement Transparency log
2	Third-party certifiers	Reproducible builds Provenance statement
3	Community certifiers	Open sourcing

There are also attempts to use formal methods to prove the security guarantees of a confidential computing system. Chen et al. [69] are introducing a principle called Proof of Being Forgotten (PoBF) and have implemented a PoBF-compliant Framework (PoCF) with a library for different hardware TEEs. Using Rust language type system and security features they have constructed a verified state machine with privacy-preserving contracts.

Individual software and hardware building block components need to be tested as well. For example, a RISC-V CPU implementation T-Head XuanTie C910/C920 turned out to be vulnerable in an attack called GhostWrite [70], [71]. The vulnerability was found using fuzz testing. The same SoC is used in BeagleV-Ahead development board and seems to have problems with non-functional PMP [72]. PMP is one of the building blocks for isolation in RISC-V and is needed, e.g., with Keystone. RISC-V International is developing the RISC-V Architectural Compatibility Test Framework that can be used to track incompatibilities.

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Although all functionalities may work as expected, there can still be side channels that leak enough information that allow, e.g., exposing a cryptographic key that is used. There are many possible side-channels [73]. Typical side-channels are power consumption, timing, and electromagnetic radiation. Side-channel testing is needed to be able to catch these problems. However, it is often difficult to decide what needs to be tested as the side-channel may be non-obvious as was the case for a speculative execution vulnerability Spectre [74].

4.5 APPROACHES FOR EMBEDDED CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING

At a high level, there are three basic approaches for confidential computing: TPM, confidential application, and confidential virtual machine-based approaches. A TPM-based approach utilizing either TPM chip or firmware TPM provides low-level fixed function functionality that is more oriented towards system integrity verification than for protecting confidential data. TPM includes confidentiality support features like sealed keys that can be decrypted only if integrity is verified to be correct. However, TPM is typically not available in non-PC hardware platforms, e.g., in ARM-based systems.

The confidential application approach is isolating one application, providing a confidential execution environment. Technologies like Intel SGX enclaves or ARM TrustZone SecureWorld Trusted Applications can be used for application protection. There are typically many constraints like memory size and functionality-related constraints like available system-level services. In this approach, applications may need modification before being able to run in a secure environment.

The third approach, a confidential virtual machine, is securing the whole operating system with applications and data by running the system in isolated confidential virtual machine. This approach is provided by AMD SEV-SNP and Intel TDX, and typically, these confidential virtual machines can run unmodified applications.

Table 2 provides a summary of different approaches for embedded confidential computing.

Table 2. Comparison of confidentiality approaches

	TPM	Confidential app	Confidential VM
Purpose	Trusted boot, secure boot, remote attestation, key storage, sealed keys	Protect specific enclave data and code	Protects entire VM including OS, applications and user data.

Granularity	System	Application	VM
HW Requirements	TPM	TEE	CVM
Suitability	Low requirements if TPM is available	Constrained by enclave size and available memory	Not applicable for constrained devices because of resource requirements
Scope	Integrity and identity	Code and data confidentiality	Full system confidentiality
Extra dev effort	Moderate but mainly protects integrity	Complex	Minimal
Use Cases	IoT device attestation, secure keys	DRM, payment apps, secure ML	Cloud workloads

4.6 PROTECTING ML MODELS AT THE EDGE

4.6.1 ML AT THE EDGE USE CASE

Traditionally, large ML models have been deployed in cloud environments. The ML model has been physically isolated by the trusted cloud provider and is only available to end-users through APIs. This concept is also known as Machine Learning as a Service (MLaaS). Although the ML model is a black box for remote observers, there are still concerns about attacks that could reveal training data and help to reverse engineer or even steal the model.

Nowadays, the use of ML models is also increasing in various end-user devices and edge nodes. This adds many new threats to ML models as the ML model is no longer physically isolated from the attackers and, in many cases, the attackers can have practically unlimited time for their attacks. Protecting the ML models requires holistic security that also requires integrity protection [75]. Some embedded system providers have started to add ML accelerators, also known as Neural Processing Units (NPUs), to their microcontroller-class systems [76], [77], [78]. There is also a discussion about the “ML at the edge” use case and mechanisms that are required to protect the ML model [79].

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Researchers have identified many privacy risks that may lead to leakage of training data private information or confidentiality of the model itself [80]. DarkneTZ by Mo et al. [81] are proposing the use of TEE to protect against such threats. Instead of running the whole model inside TEE, they have split the model so that only one layer is run inside TEE and other layers in the untrusted part of the system as there is necessarily not enough memory capacity to run the whole model inside TEE. The same group has also developed a privacy-preserving federated learning (PPFL) framework that is using TEE to protect privacy [82] using a similar architecture.

We may want to deploy a confidential ML model to do processing closer to the source of data. Input data may not need the same level of confidentiality protection if it is just environmental data like sensor measurements, e.g., temperature, humidity, or air pressure.

4.6.2 PRESENTING AND PROTECTING ML MODELS

ML models are typically shipped as a separate model file that is then read and processed in a program, e.g., Python script with specific libraries. An encrypted model file can be decrypted inside the enclave and then used in the inference process.

Small models can also be implemented as Python code. The Python-based model could be deployed as an encrypted script and used with a small Python runtime that is able to decrypt the model and then run it. However, this is challenging as in addition to the script itself many libraries need to be embedded as well. Compact Python runtimes like MicroPython [83] could run in a constrained environment like Keystone enclave.

It is also possible to deploy an ML model as a C-based code. This is an approach provided by emlearn framework [84]. The model can first be trained using a Python-based cloud framework. However, the inference phase in a device can be done using C-based native code that could be run as an enclave code (e.g., as a Keystone enclave application). This does not provide confidentiality if the Keystone enclave application is stored and loaded as non-encrypted. The Keystone framework should be extended to load encrypted enclave applications and to provide runtime support to decrypt the enclave application executable code inside the enclave. Alternatively, the model could be deployed as encrypted WebAssembly (WASM) code and there could be WebAssembly runtime inside the enclave.

Yet another potential approach could be to use FPGA-based accelerators to run ML models [85] by using the emlearn approach but then deploying the ML model as an

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encrypted FPGA bitstream. There are development boards like BeagleV-Fire [86] that also include a small FPGA.

DRAFT

5 TEE EXPERIMENTS

This Section describes practical experiments to develop a confidential computing platform in the CONFIDENTIAL6G project utilizing TEE. Most experiments are based on RISC-V Keystone which is an open-source enclave framework. Keystone is based on a confidential application concept instead of a more generic confidential virtual machine concept. The Confidential application approach requires fewer resources and is, therefore, more suitable for resource-constrained embedded computing platforms.

TEE experiments that are described in this Section are focused on RISC-V platform, but CONFIDENTIAL6G is also working on ARM TrustZone platform. CONFIDENTIAL6G deliverable D4.3 (Confidential Orchestration) is describing confidential container experiments on ARM TrustZone with OP-TEE [7] running in a Raspberry Pi device.

Many examples in this Section are using symmetric cryptography and require that there already is a shared secret between the client and the enclave. Asymmetric cryptography with platform certificates can be implemented as a future enhancement.

5.1 KEYSTONE ENCLAVES

Keystone [56] is an open-source TEE for RISC-V based systems. Keystone is based on RISC-V PMP that is used to statically partition the system into isolated enclave regions and to the rest of the system. Keystone can be used to build customizable TEEs for unmodified RISC-V platforms. PMP is RISC-V low-level memory isolation mechanism and is supported in many RISC-V development boards. Keystone is a very limited environment. PMP-based Keystone enclaves require contiguous memory areas and static partitioning is used. There is no standard support for secure storage or any filesystem that could be available for the enclave applications. Keystone enclave applications should be statically linked applications that are self-contained without a need to access the filesystem or other services.

The Keystone framework is based on four main design principles [56]:

- Leverage programmable layer and isolation primitives below the untrusted code.
- Decouple the resource management and security checks.
- Design modular layers.
- Allow to selectively include TCB only when required.

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Keystone framework is implemented using C/C++. The architecture is presented in Figure 8.

Keystone is based on RISC-V privilege levels. Security Monitor (SM) is running in a high-privilege Machine (M) mode. SM is used to configure PMP settings providing basic isolation. SM has been implemented as a plugin for OpenSBI [87], which is an open-source implementation of RISC-V Supervisory Binary Interface (SBI) [88]. SBI provides a communication mechanism between S- and M-modes. SM also provides an API for enclave and host applications that can be used for communication between host and enclave components. Keystone enclave software stack includes a runtime component running in Supervisor (S) mode and an enclave application running in User (U) mode. Runtime component Eyrie is typically used with Keystone. Keystone also includes a few demonstrator applications and a small test suite.

Figure 8. Keystone architecture

5.2 RUST SDK FOR KEYSTONE ENCLAVES

Keystone is based on C/C++. Both host and enclave applications are typically implemented using C/C++. There is also an experimental Rust-based SDK [89] for developing Keystone enclave applications. The use of Rust language helps to avoid many programming errors that are common in C/C++ development.

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CONFIDENTIAL6G project has further developed the Rust-based SDK and Keystone has also been ported to a low-end StarFive VisionFive2 hardware [90] board. There is also a Rust-based example application to establish a secure channel between the enclave and external client. The secure channel example also demonstrates confidential computing concepts as a client can pass input data to an enclave application and return results via encrypted channel and the execution is done in an isolated environment. This work is extending earlier work and now supports newer Keystone versions and can also be used with real physical hardware instead of using qemu-based simulations.

The structure of the Keystone software stack with Rust-based SDK is described in Figure 9. Orange boxes represent original unmodified Keystone components. The two blue boxes represent an enclave application and its counterpart, a host application that drives the enclave application. Both consist of the application logic, represented in yellow, which includes application specific Rust code and possibly a set of Rust crates, i.e., programming libraries. The applications must be linked with a Rust language runtime, represented in grey. An unmodified Rust language runtime is used for both the applications. Finally, Keystone Rust SDK work is represented in green.

Figure 9. Rust-based SDK for Keystone

Keystone enclave applications are using no_std Rust environment that lacks Rust standard crate (std). Instead of std, more limited core crate can be used. This is a common practice in embedded Rust development as std crate contains many features that require OS support that is not available in embedded operating systems or bare metal systems. Host components using Rust SDK can use std crate.

5.3 ENCRYPTED KEYSTONE ENCLAVE APPLICATION

Keystone framework provides an isolated execution enclave for Keystone enclave applications (eapps) and remote attestation support to verify system integrity. Eapps can setup a secure channel with a remote client and use the channel to receive input data and to send back the results of confidential computation. Although it is possible to setup a secure channel between a remote client and Keystone enclave and to protect both input data and output results from the host component and other nodes, the enclave application is copied as a plain text from Executable and Linkable Format (ELF) file that is visible to a non-trusted host component. This can be a problem if the enclave application code contains trade secrets or other sensitive information.

The obvious way to protect sensitive information is to encrypt the enclave application executable. However, there are multiple issues that need to be solved if encrypted enclave application executables are used.

- **Key management** – If the enclave application is encrypted, there should be a key that is used in decryption. The key that is used in bulk encryption should be symmetric key, e.g., AES key. The symmetric key can be wrapped to an envelope that is encrypted by a device-specific asymmetric key, e.g., RSA key. The symmetric key can be either specific to an enclave application or common for all enclave applications. All devices either use the same symmetric key or the symmetric key is device specific. The symmetric key is either provisioned to a device or generated in a device. These design choices lead to very different software architectures.
- **Encryption target** – What part of the ELF executable should be encrypted? If the whole executable is encrypted, it may not work well with existing Keystone components that expect to read an ELF file and be able to decode information in the ELF header. Encryption of the ELF file text section alone might be enough to protect sensitive algorithms unless there is also sensitive information in other sections.
- **Decrypting component** – What component should be responsible for decrypting the encrypted enclave application? Keystone runtime is probably the best candidate for that as it is passing execution control to the enclave application. Decryption could happen just before starting the enclave application.
- **Data and algorithm providers** – Eapp encryption make it also possible to separate the roles of data and algorithm providers. Eapp can be encrypted with an application specific AES key that can be different for each version.

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Keystone device should have an asymmetric key that is derived from a device secret (it is different in each device) and preferably also certified with a trusted certification authority. The algorithm provider could then use the public part of the key to encrypt the application AES key and pass that information as a license to the Keystone device via remote client that is not able to decrypt the key. The remote client can pass input data and receive output results via secure channel without having access to the eapp code.

- **Remote attestation** – If the cryptographic hash of the encrypted eapp affects to attestation evidence, that is sent as a reply to an attestation request, the result depends on architecture choices that are described earlier in this description.

As a proof of concept, a small modification to Keystone runtime has been made. The Keystone enclave application (eapp) '.text' section is PROGBITS encrypted using AES CTR mode encryption and the section name is changed to '.crypt'. Initialization vector that is used in AES encryption is stored in new section called '.iv'. This is described in Figure 10.

[Nr]	Name	Type	Address	Offset	[Nr]	Name	Type	Address	Offset
[0]		NULL	0000000000000000	00000000	[0]		NULL	0000000000000000	00000000
[1]	.text	PROGBITS	00000000000100e8	000000e8	[1]	.crypt	PROGBITS	00000000000100e8	000000e8
[2]	.rodata	PROGBITS	0000000000010350	00000350	[2]	.rodata	PROGBITS	0000000000010350	00000350
[3]	.comment	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	0000035c	[3]	.comment	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	0000035c
[4]	.riscv.attributes	RISCV_ATTRIBUTE	0000000000000000	0000037f	[4]	.riscv.attributes	RISCV_ATTRIBUTE	0000000000000000	0000037f
[5]	.debug_aranges	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	000003b0	[5]	.debug_aranges	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	000003b0
[6]	.debug_info	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	00000440	[6]	.debug_info	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	00000440
[7]	.debug_abbrev	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	00000ae9	[7]	.debug_abbrev	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	00000ae9
[8]	.debug_line	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	00000d19	[8]	.debug_line	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	00000d19
[9]	.debug_frame	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	000013c8	[9]	.debug_frame	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	000013c8
[10]	.debug_str	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	000014e0	[10]	.debug_str	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	000014e0
[11]	.debug_line_str	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	00001746	[11]	.debug_line_str	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	00001746
[12]	.debug_loclists	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	000019c0	[12]	.debug_loclists	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	000019c0
[13]	.debug_rnglists	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	000020b0	[13]	.debug_rnglists	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	000020b0
[14]	.syntab	SYMTAB	0000000000000000	000020e0	[14]	.iv	PROGBITS	0000000000000000	00003000
[15]	.strtab	STRTAB	0000000000000000	000024e8	[15]	.syntab	SYMTAB	0000000000000000	00003010
[16]	.shstrtab	STRTAB	0000000000000000	000025eb	[16]	.strtab	STRTAB	0000000000000000	00003430
					[17]	.shstrtab	STRTAB	0000000000000000	00003533

Figure 10. Encrypted text section added to an ELF file

When an enclave application (eapp) is loaded, an encrypted section '.crypt', if it exists, is loaded as a text segment instead of a section '.text'. Additionally, another section '.iv' is also read. Keystone runtime loader is then decrypting the '.crypt' section while reading it using AES CTR mode decryption using a fixed AES key with the content of the '.iv' section as an initialization vector. Because CTR mode does not need padding, it fits to existing '.text' segment and only section name be modified and a new small '.iv' section needs to be added. Fixed AES key is used now as this is just a proof-of-concept implementation.

Figure 11. Encrypted application text segment is decrypted inside the enclave

A more generic alternative is to get the application-specific AES key from the algorithm provider and to combine this with a secure channel between a data provider node and a device node. Secure channel could be based on attested TLS so that the handshake operation also includes exchange of remote attestation messages and integrity verification. There can also be a certification authority that is used to certify the public keys of the actors as described in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Algorithm and data providers and certificates

5.4 PYTHON-BASED EXECUTION ENVIRONMENT

Although native code enclave applications can be used to implement confidential processing of sensitive data, the enclave application itself can be analysed and reverse-engineered as it is not encrypted. This can be a serious problem if the application contains trade secrets that require protection. One way to solve this

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problem is to use a special enclave application loader that can load encrypted applications that are then decrypted inside the enclave before execution. Another alternative is to use encrypted scripts and script runtime that can decrypt these scripts.

MicroPython [83] is a Python language implementation that is optimized for microcontrollers. MicroPython can be built for many environments, and it is also possible to build it as an embeddable library. MicroPython embeddable library can then be linked with a Keystone enclave application. It was rather easy to experiment with MicroPython and create an example where the client could send an encrypted script to Keystone enclave (assuming shared secret) and the script is decrypted and run. MicroPython function `mp_embed_exec_str()` can be used to start the script. Script output can be passed to the enclave application by creating and linking a custom `mp_hal_stdout_tx_strn_cooked()` function implementation with the MicroPython implementation. The enclave code can then encrypt the script output and send it back to the client. In a similar way there is also a function called `mp_hal_stdin_rx_char()` that can be used to pass standard input to the script. However, MicroPython configuration is rather complex process, and documentation does not cover much of these embeddable library issues. Support for new platforms like Keystone enclaves requires more work. One big problem is that as Keystone enclaves do not support any filesystem abstraction, it is not possible to implement Python import statements. Therefore, simple embeddable Keystone MicroPython enclave can only run simple Python scripts that do not import additional modules severely limiting the use of the environment. Additionally, it seems that MicroPython implementation of Python `input()` statement also requires Python `sys` module and therefore `stdin` cannot be directly used as a script data input without modifications or advanced configuration settings.

There are ways to fix these issues. Keystone implementation could be enhanced so that there is a filesystem abstraction with a root filesystem that contains the MicroPython modules. Another alternative is to modify the MicroPython implementation so that the main script and the modules could be loaded together as a one package and the import statements could then pick the referenced modules from the package. MicroPython includes also binary container file format (called `.mpy` files), but it seems that it only provides precompiled versions of Python script files and does not bundle multiple binary scripts to one file. MicroPython provides a tool called `mpy-cross` for that. However, MicroPython code that is used with `mpy-cross` only refers to 32-bit RISC-V environment and there is no support for 64-bit RISC-V that is used in Keystone build configuration. Extending MicroPython with 64-bit RISC-V support should be considered. It might be that the

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lack of 64-bit RISC-V support is only for the binary container file format as it is possible to install MicroPython package using buildroot.

Figure 13. Encrypted Python script is decrypted inside the eapp

There is also another platform called CircuitPython [91] that is also targeted for microcontroller class devices. CircuitPython is also built on top of MicroPython. CircuitPython is mainly trying to build easy-to-use Python development environment for supported microcontroller platforms. CircuitPython recommends the use of binary container format (.mpy) library files.

5.5 WEBASSEMBLY-BASED EXECUTION ENVIRONMENT

Another potential environment for confidential script/bytecode execution inside the Keystone enclave is WebAssembly (WASM) [92]. WebAssembly includes a portable bytecode format and interfaces to interact with a host environment. WebAssembly is targeted to efficiently run applications on web pages. The idea resembles older web technologies like Java applets, Microsoft ActiveX, and Macromedia Flash. Nowadays, similar very dynamic web pages are typically implemented using JavaScript. WebAssembly could bring back the use of more compact bytecode format and with just-in-time compilation to native code also more efficiency by utilizing standardized mechanisms and formats. WebAssembly is also meant to be an object code format that can be supported from multiple source code languages. WebAssembly runtime has also gained interest for non-web usage. Portable runtime could be integrated to embedded systems to implement script-based extensions to these systems.

It is possible to run WebAssembly runtime inside the Keystone enclave, which is a very limited bare metal environment. Keystone enclaves do not have filesystem support, but WebAssembly programs are supposed to run inside a web browser in

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a sandbox, so this is not a critical limitation. Keystone enclave applications do not support multiple threads and processes. This is also a limitation that may be possible as it only rules out certain kind of applications. The key issue is to find a suitable WebAssembly runtime implementation that could run inside the Keystone enclave.

Figure 14. Encrypted WebAssembly bytecode is decrypted inside the eapp

There are lots of different WebAssembly runtime implementations [93]. In addition to a bytecode interpreter, there is also a standardization effort called the WebAssembly System Interface (WASI) for external interfaces. Many implementations are claimed to be embeddable and lightweight with a small footprint. For example, WebAssembly Micro Runtime (WAMR) [94] supports multiple platforms and even mentions TEE support (Intel SGX). Microsoft Hyperlight-Wasm [95] relies on Hyperlight library [96] that can be used to create micro virtual machines (sandboxes) that are optimized for securely running untrusted code with minimal impact. Hyperlight-Wasm currently supports only Linux and Windows.

After a short evaluation of different alternatives, a small Rust-based WebAssembly runtime implementation called TinyWasm [97] was selected as a basis for our proof-of-concept implementation. TinyWasm supports Rust no_std environment, the code does not contain any unsafe code blocks, and the implementation passes WebAssembly core test suites.

A proof-of-concept implementation is implemented using our VECTOR Rust SDK library. A secure channel is established between a remote client and an enclave code that is running TinyWASM runtime. WebAssembly program can be sent from the remote client using a secure channel. Messaging can also include parameters

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for the calculation. Optionally, parameters can be read from the local environment as well.

5.6 APACHE TEACLAVE

The Keystone-project is not active anymore. Most RISC-V related activity is now in CoVE-related projects [44]. However, those are based on the confidential virtual machine approach. A more limited confidential application approach could still be valid for resource constrained devices as the current low-end RISC-V development boards do not support RISC-V hypervisor extension that is required by the CoVE specification.

Currently, RISC-V support is missing in many cross-platform frameworks, or it is implemented using Keystone as with Certifier [65]. However, Certifier is based on C/C++ as new system software code should preferably be built using a language like Rust that provides better protection against coding errors. Apache Teaclave [98] as Rust-based framework could be a good candidate to support also RISC-V. Consider what is needed to port Apache Teaclave to RISC-V platform perhaps partly utilizing Keystone components. Teaclave already has APIs to support ARM TrustZone and Intel SGX.

6 FHE AND CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING

6.1 INTRODUCTION

In principle, FHE can be seen as the ideal solution for confidential computing in general, including for embedded devices. By allowing computation to be performed directly over encrypted data, it provides formal guarantees of security irrespective of hardware or deployment environment. In practice, however, the computational overhead incurred by current FHE schemes limits its practicality even in larger servers, putting in question whether it is at all feasible to deploy FHE-based confidential computing on resource-constrained environments.

Aiming at accessing such possibilities, this report considers the use of FHE-based confidential computing in two scenarios:

1. A resource-constrained device acts as a client in a multi-party protocol that includes large servers running some of the FHE-based confidential-computing solutions developed in Task 2.3 [99]. In this scenario, we evaluate the performance of the main client-side operations, namely encryption, decryption, and encoding functions. In addition to standard FHE encryption operations for Ring Learning With Errors (RLWE) ciphertexts, we also consider the use of transciphering techniques, which are often employed to minimize communication costs and are especially relevant for embedded devices with limited network capacity.
2. FHE-based computation running directly on a resource-constrained device. In this scenario, we focus on small applications related to the use-cases developed in CONFIDENTIAL6G work package 5 and briefly described in the deliverable D5.1 [100].

6.2 FHE CLIENT-SIDE COMPUTATION

6.2.1 OVERVIEW OF FHE PROCEDURES

In this section, we recall the main client-side FHE operations, which we benchmark in the following sections. A full description and formal definitions of FHE operations and underlying (R)LWE cryptosystems are provided in CONFIDENTIAL6G deliverable [99]. For some ring $\mathcal{R}_q = \mathbb{Z}_q[X]/(X^N + 1)$, we have:

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- **RLWE Encryption:** Given a secret key $s \in \mathcal{R}_q$ and a message $m \in \mathcal{R}_p$, sample polynomials $a \in \mathcal{R}_q$ uniformly at random from \mathcal{R}_q and $e \in \mathcal{R}_q$ from a discrete Gaussian distribution with mean 0 and standard deviation σ . Let $\Delta = p/q$ be a scaling factor, compute $b \leftarrow a \cdot s + m \Delta + e$, return (a, b) .
- **RLWE Decryption:** Given a ciphertext $(a, b) \in \mathcal{R}_q^2$ and a secret key $s \in \mathcal{R}_q$, compute and return $m \leftarrow \lfloor (b - a \cdot s) / \Delta \rfloor$.
- **Message encoding:** FHE schemes adopt different types of encoding to extend their computation capabilities. The most common ones consist of exploiting ring isomorphisms to embed multiple messages from \mathbb{Z}_p into \mathcal{R}_q and enable Single-Instruction-Multiple-Data (SIMD)-like operations. Let $m_i \in \mathbb{Z}_p$ for $i \in [0, N)$ be a list of input messages, an encoded message $\hat{m} \in \mathcal{R}_p$ can be produced by computing $\hat{m} \leftarrow \text{INTT}(m_0, m_1, \dots, m_{N-1})$, where INTT is the inverse of the negacyclic-wrapped Number Theoretic Transform [101].

6.2.2 BASIC ARITHMETIC PERFORMANCE

In all procedures described above, the most expensive operation is the multiplication of elements in \mathcal{R}_q . Naive multiplication algorithms (*e.g.*, schoolbook multiplication) would take time $O(N^2)$ to compute it, but one can improve performance by mapping the ring to a product of small fields, which can be multiplied in linear time. This mapping is usually performed using DFT-like convolution algorithms such as the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) and the Number Theoretic Transform (NTT). In both cases, the overall multiplication complexity is reduced to quasilinear while all other procedures remain linear in the size of polynomials. We benchmarked FFTs, inverse FFTs, multiplications, and additions for polynomials of size $N = 2048$. Table 3 shows the results.

Table 3. Execution time, in microseconds, of the main arithmetic operations required by FHE schemes for polynomials of size $N = 2048$. Each number is the average of 1 million executions.

Implementation	Device	FFT	IFFT	Multiplication	Addition
Portable	Mobile	21.1	26.2	1.2	0.8
	Cloud	8.43	11.12	0.5	0.3
AVX512-optimized	Cloud	2.58	2.65	0.5	0.3

We ran our experiments using the arithmetic implementations available in the MOSFHET library [102]. We compiled MOSFHET's portable build using CLANG 17 for ARM aarch64 and benchmarked it using a Mobile device with a Cortex-X2

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processor at 2.8 GHz. For comparison, Table 3 also provides MOSFHET's original benchmark, performed on an AWS *m6i.metal* instance, using an Intel Xeon Platinum 8375C (Ice Lake) CPU at 3.5GHz. While significantly slower than the AVX512-optimized version available in MOSFHET, the Mobile device was only up to 2.5 times slower than the large cloud server when running the Portable version of MOSFHET. Considering the major difference in size and computational resources between these two environments, we see it as a highly positive result for the feasibility of FHE client-side operations in mobile devices. More details about the implementations and employed techniques are described in MOSFHET's paper [102], partially developed in the context of Task 2.3 of this project.

6.2.3 ENCRYPTION, ENCODING, AND DECRYPTION FUNCTIONS

Based on the results on Section 6.2.2, we estimate the costs of the main high-level client-side FHE operations:

- **RLWE Encryption:** Considering the use of FFTs, encryption is computed as follows:

$$(a, b = \text{IFFT}(\text{FFT}(a) \cdot \text{FFT}(s)) + m \Delta + e)$$

Assuming, $\text{FFT}(s)$ can be precomputed, this process requires one forward FFT, one reverse FFT, one multiplication, and two additions. This would result in a total cost of 50.1 microseconds per encryption, enabling almost 20 thousand encryptions per second single-threaded on our mobile device.

- **RLWE Decryption:** Given a ciphertext (a,b) and the secret key s , decryption could be computed as follows:

$$m = \text{round}((b - \text{IFFT}(\text{FFT}(a) \cdot \text{FFT}(s))) / \Delta)$$

Which would result in a similar cost to encryption. In this case, however, besides pre-computing $\text{FFT}(s)$, one can also ask the cloud server to provide $\text{FFT}(a)$ (recall that we are in a two-party computation scenario where the client communicates with a server between encryption and decryption). Considering that, decryption cost is only one IFFT, one multiplication, and one subtraction, which takes only 28.2 microseconds.

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- **Message encoding:** This process varies according to the choice of FHE scheme and application. Most commonly, it would consist of a single IFFT (or inverse NTT), which costs 26.2 microseconds in our mobile device.

6.2.4 TRANSCIPHERING

Transciphering (or Hybrid Homomorphic Encryption, HHE) is an established solution for eliminating ciphertext expansion in HE schemes, saving communication and storage resources. It consists of encrypting data using a symmetric cipher that can be later homomorphically evaluated to recover data in an FHE ciphertext. In this way, data can be stored and communicated without any expansion, and the ciphertext only expands at processing time. It is especially important in the context of resource-constrained environments, as devices often have limited network capabilities.

In this project, we contributed to development of efficient ways of homomorphically evaluating Mixed-Filter-Permutator (MFP) ciphers and introduced methods that are up to 2 orders of magnitude faster than previous literature. See the paper [103] for detailed results and discussion. While our published results focus on performance for the server, this section analyses the cipher from the point of view of a client running in a resource constrained scenario.

We implemented a cleartext evaluation of the Margrethe cipher [104] in Python and evaluated in the same Mobile environment described in Section 6.2.2. On a single thread, our python script takes 97.2 seconds to produce a key stream for encrypting 320 thousand 4-bit messages, a cost of just 0.3ms per message or 76 microseconds per bit. These numbers could be significantly improved in optimized implementation, but our proof-of-concept Python script already clearly shows the practicality of using these techniques.

6.3 FHE COMPUTATION

We now assess the possibility of running the FHE computation directly in a resource-constrained device. For this case, we consider the Homomorphic WiSARDs framework for FHE-based encrypted weightless neural network training [105], partially developed in the context of Task 3.3. Since this framework only supports Intel architecture, we run it on a consumer-grade Intel desktop (Intel Core i7-12700k at 5.0 GHz and 64GB of RAM) with limited resources. Particularly, we restrict it to single-thread execution and measure the use of memory for different sizes of input. We consider the same datasets as [105], namely, the MNIST dataset of handwritten digits [106], the HAM10000 dataset of skin cancer images [107], and the Wisconsin Breast Cancer tabular dataset [108]. Table 4 shows our results. The

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training set size is given in the number of images (for MNIST and HAM10000) or table rows (for Wisconsin). Results that would take more than 3 hours are estimated.

Table 4. Execution time and memory usage for the FHE evaluation of Homomorphic WiSARDs.

	MNIST				HAM10000			Wisconsin
	T	S	M	L	S	M	L	
Training set size	1000	7500	30000	60000	1002	4006	8012	569
Time	12m16s	2h34m	28h55m	156h15m	54m13s	9h19m	43h30m	11s
Memory	177MiB	427MiB	1.2GiB	3.4GiB	638MiB	1.8GiB	6.0GiB	132MiB

Memory use is often one of the main bottlenecks in FHE computation, especially in resource-constrained environments. Table 4 shows that the Homomorphic WiSARDs framework is capable of operating with relatively small memory requirements for several datasets. In particular, the smallest subset of MNIST (where only 1000 images are provided as input), requires only 177MiB of memory, which would be feasible for most mobile devices and many modern microcontrollers. On the other hand, larger datasets have memory requirements in the order of several gigabytes, being likely unpractical for such platforms, especially as the single-thread execution time for these larger cases is also in the order of several days.

7 CONCLUSIONS

While confidential computing is often associated with cloud-based processing, there are numerous scenarios where transferring data to the cloud is suboptimal due to latency constraints and data transfer limitations. In such cases, processing data closer to its source, at the edge, is more efficient. This necessitates enabling confidential computing capabilities on edge nodes, even when these nodes are resource-constrained and cannot support traditional confidential virtual machines.

Extending confidential computing across the Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI) continuum allows orchestration systems to dynamically select the most suitable location for secure computation. This approach minimizes data transfer, reduces latency, and optimizes power consumption.

Our work explores this direction by implementing a confidential computing framework on a RISC-V-based embedded platform using the open-source Keystone enclave. We enhanced the framework with experimental support for code confidentiality and evaluated the use of script and bytecode runtimes, such as Python and WebAssembly, within the enclave. While these runtimes offer flexibility, they also introduce complexity and pose challenges in meeting system interface requirements within the lightweight Keystone environment. Runtime size constraints also remain a limiting factor despite the use of minimal implementations. Rust was chosen as the implementation language due to its strong memory safety guarantees.

Furthermore, although FHE is typically considered too computationally intensive for embedded systems, we successfully benchmarked client-side FHE operations. This enables secure workload uploads to cloud services lacking TEEs, thereby broadening the range of viable service providers, including European alternatives to dominant U.S.-based platforms. We also evaluated the performance of Homomorphic WiSARDs FHE in embedded environments.

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